

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

 @pinagpalapublishingservices **Search**

 pinagpala_publishing **Search**

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com **Search**

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.172-177, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

EVALUATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN UNDERSTANDING CULTURE, SOCIETY, AND POLITICS: BASIS FOR INNOVATIVE INSTRUCTIONAL MODULE

A Master's Thesis

Presented to

The Faculty of the Graduate Program

School of Teacher Education

The National Teachers College

In Partial Fulfillment

of the Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Education

Major in Social Science

by

RONALD HERMEDILLA ABESAMIS

Adviser: HERNANDO L. BERNAL JR., LPT, PhD, FLPI

Date of Completion: May 2025

ABSTRACT

Instructional materials as educational tools enhance effective teaching and learning outcomes by providing clear, engaging, and meaningful experiences. This mixed-method study evaluated existing instructional materials used in the subject Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) for Grade 12 students at Quezon National High School during the School Year 2023–2024. Using the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI 1.5) and Merrill's Principles of Instruction, the study assessed the effectiveness and level of implementation of UCSP modules. Quantitative data were analyzed using weighted means, while qualitative feedback from interviews and focus group discussions were analyzed thematically. Results showed that existing instructional materials were moderately effective, particularly in learning goal alignment and reusability, but needed improvement in content quality, accessibility, and motivation. Findings suggested the integration of differentiated activities, adaptive feedback, and inclusive design features. Recommendations include periodic evaluation, enhancement of content relevance, and development of innovative, learner-centered UCSP modules aligned with Merrill's instructional framework.

Keywords: Instructional Materials, LORI 1.5, Merrill's Principles, UCSP, Social Science Education

I. INTRODUCTION

This study focuses on evaluating and improving instructional materials in the subject Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). In today's teaching context, educators rely on various instructional tools to enhance clarity and engagement. However, social studies subjects like UCSP are often criticized for being monotonous and lacking innovation. The researcher observed that

Copyright © 2025 by Pinagpala Publishing Services

Indexed at Google Scholar, Zenodo, OpenAire, Philippne eJournals, Google, Yahoo, PPS Website

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.172-177, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

UCSP materials used at Quezon National High School had limited relevance, typographical errors, and outdated examples. These issues prompted the need to evaluate the effectiveness of current materials and to develop innovative, learner-centered modules.

The theoretical foundation of the study was grounded in Merrill's First Principles of Instruction and the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI 1.5) framework. Merrill's principles emphasize problem-centered learning, activation, demonstration, application, and integration, while LORI 1.5 evaluates instructional materials based on nine dimensions—content quality, alignment, feedback, motivation, design, usability, accessibility, reusability, and standards compliance. Integrating these models ensured that the evaluation covered both pedagogical and technical aspects of instructional design.

This research aimed to determine the effectiveness of existing UCSP materials, evaluate the level of implementation of Merrill's principles, identify common instructional challenges, and develop an innovative module aligned with both frameworks. The findings are intended to support teachers in delivering effective, engaging, and inclusive UCSP instruction.

II. Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness and implementation of existing instructional materials in the subject **Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP)** and to develop an **innovative instructional module** that addressed the identified gaps in content quality, instructional strategies, and assessment design for Grade 12 students of Quezon National High School for the School Year 2023–2024.

RESEARCH METHODS

III. Research Design

A mixed-method research design utilizing the triangulation approach was employed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Quantitative data were gathered through survey questionnaires using LORI 1.5 and Merrill's instructional principles to evaluate existing materials. Qualitative data were collected through interviews and focus group discussions with UCSP teachers, providing contextual insights into instructional practices.

The study was conducted at Quezon National High School. Participants included one head teacher, two master teachers, and eleven senior high school teachers handling UCSP. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents with at least three years of teaching experience in UCSP. The instruments underwent expert validation and reliability testing.

Ethical standards were observed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Data collection involved distributing questionnaires and conducting interviews. Quantitative data were analyzed using weighted means with corresponding descriptive ratings, while qualitative data were subjected to thematic analysis. Triangulation of both data types ensured reliability and validity.

IV. Population and Sampling

The study involves one head teacher, two master teachers specializing in social sciences and related fields, and eleven senior high school teachers who teach UCSP at Quezon National High School. These participants were purposively selected as qualified evaluators of the current UCSP teaching materials to aid in developing an innovative instructional module. The selection criteria include having at least three years of experience in their respective positions and specializations, teaching UCSP at Quezon National High School, and being willing to participate in the study.

V. Research Instrument

The study involves one head teacher, two master teachers, and eleven UCSP teachers from Quezon National High School, purposively selected to evaluate existing UCSP instructional materials and help develop a new module based on Merrill's Principles of Instruction—Demonstration, Problem-Centeredness, Activation, Application, and Integration. A Likert-scale questionnaire will be used to gather their evaluations, comments, and suggestions. The instrument was validated by three education experts and tested for reliability with 13 respondents.

VI. DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

After securing necessary permits from the Schools Division Office of Quezon Province and Quezon National High School, the researcher conducted the study using the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI) to evaluate UCSP instructional materials. The survey, distributed both online and in print, assessed aspects such as content quality, goal alignment, motivation, interaction, and accessibility.

For SOP 1, data were quantitatively analyzed to determine the effectiveness of existing materials.

For SOP 2, another section of the questionnaire, guided by Merrill's Principles of Instruction, examined how these materials were applied in classrooms. Follow-ups ensured complete and accurate responses, and a statistician assisted in data analysis. For SOP 3, focus group discussions with master and classroom teachers were conducted, with results analyzed thematically to identify key insights. Finally, for SOP 4, the researcher developed new UCSP instructional materials aligned with LORI 1.5 and Merrill's Principles, incorporating feedback from participants to ensure relevance and quality.

VII. Ethical Considerations

The study followed a strict ethical framework ensuring the well-being, privacy, and rights of all UCSP teacher participants. All procedures adhered to ethical standards emphasizing informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, data security, non-maleficence, and transparency to maintain research integrity.

Under the Data Protection Law, personal information was used solely for research purposes and securely deleted or anonymized after completion. Confidentiality and anonymity were protected through coded responses and secure data storage.

Participants provided informed consent after being fully briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks or benefits, with the freedom to withdraw anytime without consequence.

For document analysis, instructional materials from the Department of Education were handled responsibly, respecting copyright and intellectual property rights through proper citation.

Finally, participants were informed that the study aimed to evaluate UCSP teaching materials, requiring only about 10–15 minutes of voluntary participation through surveys or interviews, with no penalties for withdrawal.

VIII. RESULTS

The evaluation of UCSP instructional materials using the LORI 1.5 framework yielded a general weighted mean of 2.94, interpreted as moderately effective. Among the nine LORI criteria, Learning Goal Alignment (WM = 3.67) and Reusability (WM = 3.47) obtained the highest ratings, while Content Quality (WM = 2.47) and Accessibility (WM = 2.60) scored lowest. Teachers noted that many examples

were outdated and that materials lacked inclusivity features such as SPED-friendly formats or mobile accessibility.

In terms of Merrill's Principles, the modules were moderately implemented, particularly in sequencing content from simple to complex (WM = 3.47) and contextualizing lessons (WM = 3.20). However, students had limited opportunities for self-discovery and problem-solving tasks (WM = 2.87). Teachers emphasized the need for more experiential activities that link theory to real-world issues.

Qualitative findings supported the quantitative results. Teachers reported that UCSP materials lacked engagement, were text-heavy, and insufficiently interactive. Feedback mechanisms were rigid, and the modules offered minimal adaptability to student progress. These insights confirmed the need for innovative instructional designs integrating gamification, multimedia components, and differentiated learning paths.

IX. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate that while UCSP instructional materials generally align with learning objectives, they fall short in engagement, inclusivity, and responsiveness. The moderate effectiveness rating indicates potential for improvement, especially in adapting materials to diverse learners' needs. Merrill's and LORI's frameworks both highlight the importance of interactive, learner-centered, and problem-based instructional design. The findings validate the call for continuous evaluation and revision of learning resources.

By integrating updated content and innovative design strategies, UCSP materials can better promote higher-order thinking, critical reflection, and active participation. Incorporating visual aids, localized examples, and reflective assessments can further enhance student motivation and understanding. This aligns with educational innovation principles emphasizing engagement, relevance, and inclusivity.

X. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that existing UCSP instructional materials are moderately effective and moderately implemented based on Merrill's and LORI frameworks. While they align with intended competencies, they require enhancements in content relevance, accessibility, and interactivity. Teachers' feedback underscored the necessity of innovative, learner-driven, and differentiated materials that cater to multiple intelligences and real-world application.

Recommendations include periodic review of materials, integration of updated and contextualized content, and incorporation of varied assessment tools. It is also recommended that schools adopt a participatory approach in module design, engaging both teachers and learners in content development. Future studies may explore broader variables such as student performance outcomes and cross-school comparisons for comprehensive improvement of social science instruction.

REFERENCES

- Abad, (2025). The impact of teaching materials on instructional design and teacher development.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2025.1577721/full>
- Abdelraheem, Reison and Brown, A. H. (2019): Instructional Materials in teaching Social Science Education.
- Bai, N. (2023). Educational challenges in the Philippines. PIDS - Philippine Institute for the Development Studies . <https://pids.gov.ph/details/news/in-the-news/educational-challenges-in-the-philippines>

- Balita, A. B., & Salvador, N. T. (2023). Differentiated instruction and higher order thinking skills of grade 12 students in understanding culture. *International Journal of Advance Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(6), 425-451. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/1-IJAMS-JUNE-2023-425-451.pdf>.
- Bordia, D. (2022). The Importance of Instructional Materials. <https://blog.teachmint.com/the-importance-of-instructional-materials/>
- Cempron, D. N. L. (2021). An inquiry on the underlying instructional materials in social studies. *Advance (A SAGE Preprints Community)*. <https://doi.org/10.31124/advance.14846868.v1>.
- Crisolo, O. R., Camposano, S., & Rogayan Jr., D. V. (2021). Relevance of social studies in the 21st century society: Students' perspectives. *International Journal of Didactical Studies*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.33902/IJODS.2021169729>.
- Festiyed, Desnita, Afradisca, and Sari (2020). Availability of learning resources for enrichment learning at senior high school in West Sumatra. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1481/1/012119>
- Hedgepeth and Paska, (2021). Reflecting on a New Year: The Indispensable Role of Social Studies Teachers. <https://www.socialstudies.org/news/reflecting-new-year-indispensable-role-social-studies-teachers>
- Hwa, (2020). What Do Effective Instructional Material Look Like?. <https://riseprogramme.org/blog/effective-instructional-materials.html>
- Isa, (2021). LORI (Learning Object Review Instrument). <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/lori-learning-object-review-instrument/243950974>
- Istance, D. (2019). Approaches to pedagogical innovation and why they matter. Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/approaches-to-pedagogical-innovation-and-why-they-matter/>
- Kurt, S., (2022). Merrill's principles of instruction. <https://educationlibrary.org/merrills-principles-of-instruction/>
- Li J. and Wang R., (2024). RETRACTED ARTICLE: Determining the role of innovative teaching practices, sustainable learning, and the adoption of e-learning tools in leveraging academic motivation for students' mental well-being <https://bmcpyschology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40359-024-01639-3>
- Mateo, J., (2020). DepEd hit for lack of learning materials. PhilStar Global. <https://www.philstar.com/other-sections/education-and-home/2019/06/27/1929821/dep-ed-hit-lack-learning-materials>
- McCombes, S. (2023, June 22). Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. Scribbr. Retrieved May 7, 2024, <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Ndukwe, (2022). The use of instructional materials. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/use-instructional-materials-ndukwe-emmanuel-sanctus>
- Oxford Learning, (2023). The Power of Happiness and Connection in Education. <https://oxfordlearning.com/the-power-of-happiness-and-connection-in-education/>

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.172-177, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

- Pappas, C. (2021). Merrill's principles of instruction: The definitive guide. ELearning Industry- Instructional Designs. <https://elearningindustry.com/merrills-principles-instruction-definitive>
- Pedroso, J. E. P., & Magno, L. B. (2023). Teaching practices of social studies teachers in facilitating self-directed learning of senior high school students in the Philippines. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4 (7), 2300-2311. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE7/IJRPR15544.pdf>
- Rappler (2023). PH still among lowest in math, science, reading in global student assessment. Rappler Global. <https://www.rappler.com/nation/for-second-time-ph-ranks-among-lowest-pisa-2022/>
- Rogel, G. (2023). Mastery and achievement levels and experiences of Grade 11 HUMSS learners using the teacher-made learning activity sheet in understanding culture, society and politics https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371935952_
- Saha, S. (2020). Merrill's principles of instruction: A guide to effective teaching. Retrieved from <https://www.simplimba.com/merrills-principles-of-instruction/>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17410799

